

Dendrochronological analysis of tabernacle from Berg church, Norway C2911

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CATS dendro report 4 (9th January 2014)

In this report, the dendrochronological analysis of the tabernacle from Berg church in Norway is described. This research was commissioned to contribute to the PhD research of Kristin Kausland, within the research project, 'After the Black Death: Painting and Polychrome Sculpture in Norway, 1350–1550'. This project is co-led by Noëlle Streeton and Tine Frøysaker, based in Conservation Studies, University of Oslo (UiO). Funding for this study was issued to Noëlle Streeton and Kristin Kausland in 2013 by the Department of Archaeology, Conservation and History (IAKH) and the Faculty of Humanities, UiO.

Fig. 1. Berg tabernacle. View of the piece.

The tabernacle consists of the tabernacle itself and doors. Timbers from the tabernacle and the right hand door were examined. The tabernacle is in the form of a plank frame with metal door (see fig. 1). The frame consists of two plank layers. Behind this front is a plank-built cabinet, though without a backing (see figs 2 and 3). The right-hand-side door (fig. 4) consists of a single oak plank within a frame. The back of the construction was without paint, allowing access in some instances to a clean transverse section, and in others to the longitudinal section of the planks.

Additionally, paint was worn away from parts of the front of the tabernacle, so that the tree-rings of the front could also be accessed. The painted plank of the door could also be analysed, due to exposure of the tree-rings in longitudinal section where the lower part of the painting is worn.

In all, seven wood elements from the Berg tabernacle were analysed dendrochronologically; two front planks (P1 & P4) and one back plank (P5) from the plank-built frontal, three planks (P7, P8 & P9) from the back cabinet and one plank from the right-hand-side door (see fig 2).

Fig. 2. Berg tabernacle. Schematic diagram of the wood elements in the tabernacle. The elements analysed are marked in green.

Measuring

As described in the report on the dendrochronological analysis of the Slagen altarpiece (*CATS dendro report 2*, Daly 2013b), non-invasive analysis can be carried out in certain circumstances, and this was a priority for the altarpieces being analysed in this project. All measurements from the Berg tabernacle were taken from parts

where the wood grain was already exposed. The transverse section of the wood was visible on three planks, so these were photographed and measured from these sections (fig. 6). All other measurements are from the longitudinal sections. Macro photographs of the surfaces, along with a ruler for scale, were taken. These photos were then stitched together using Adobe Photoshop (version 11.0.2), and measured using an application "Able Image Analyser". Here, the scale is used to calibrate the picture, and the measurements are made to 1/100mm precision. For calculation of the t-value ("t-test") "CROS" (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) is used, embedded in the program "DENDRO" (Tyers, 1997). Ian Tyers, Sheffield, has contributed to this analysis with data comparison and invaluable discussion.

Fig. 3. Berg tabernacle. View of the underside of the corpus showing the cabinet or box.

The results

As mentioned above, the tabernacle consists of a cabinet without a back, fronted by an iron gate, framed by a wide plank-built frame. Plank doors, one left and one right, were hinged to this.

Fig. 4. Berg tabernacle. The right hand side door featuring Saint Sunniva. The painting is worn at the lowermost part, allowing access to the longitudinal section of the oak, enabling measurement.

The right door

Measurements of the tree-ring widths were made on the longitudinal section of the wood at the base, where the painting of Saint Sunniva is worn (fig. 4). Through measurements from two places along the plank, all initial errors were resolved and the resulting tree-ring curve is dated. Only heartwood is preserved on the plank, and it covers the period AD1271 to AD1478. Allowing for missing sapwood, the felling date for the tree from which this plank was made is estimated to after AD 1488 (fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Berg tabernacle. Diagram showing the chronological position of the dated elements. The green shading indicates interpretation of the dating results (see text below).

Tabernacle frame

The plank-built frame consisted of back and front planks (see fig. 2). Two of the front planks (P1 & P4) were analysed, as paint had worn off on parts, on the longitudinal section. One of the backing planks (P5) was also analysed, where its transverse section was exposed at the underside of the tabernacle (fig. 6). The back plank (P5) contained 124 rings, all heartwood, and covers the period AD 1266 to 1389. The tree that was used for this plank was felled after AD 1399. The front planks (vertical right hand side (P4) and the lower horizontal plank (P1)) also consist only of heartwood and contained just 62 and 82 rings respectively. Only one of these, the horizontal plank 1, is dated. The tree used to make this plank was felled after AD 1480 (fig. 5).

The cabinet

Three of the four planks that make up the cabinet sides were analysed (fig. 2). The right (P7) and left (P8) planks were exposed on the transverse end while the bottom plank (P9) was analysed on the exposed longitudinal surface. Clear measurement of the tree-ring series was possible and all three of these are dated. Again, no sapwood was preserved on any of these planks. The felling date for the trees from which the planks were made is estimated to: P9, after AD 1477, P7, after AD 1484 and P8, after AD 1489 (fig. 5).

Fig. 6. Berg tabernacle. The end-grain (transverse section) visible on plank P5. Measurements of the tree-rings were taken from macro-photographs of this exposed section.

Interpretation

As no sapwood is preserved on any of the analysed components, the dendrochronological analysis can only give us a *terminus post quem* for the construction of the Berg tabernacle, at after c. AD 1489. However there is one extra piece of evidence that might allow a more detailed interpretation of the dating. The tabernacle has been repaired, in modern times, at plank 8 (fig. 7). It is on plank 8 that the outermost surviving tree-ring is preserved, and this plank's outermost rings are adjacent to this repair. So it is rather possible that further outer rings were removed from plank 8 during the repair of this part of the cabinet. Rather than suggesting that this would place the dating of the building of the tabernacle to a later period, it might be suggested that the outer, removed rings on the now incomplete plank 8 were in fact sapwood rings. This is because the sapwood rings are highly susceptible to decay, worm or rot. That the tabernacle needed repair at just this part of its construction might be because the sapwood had not been trimmed away in the original manufacture, and that this sapwood had become so worn that repair was necessary. If this is indeed the construction history of the piece, we can suggest that plank 8 could be preserved very close to the heartwood/sapwood boundary. Then we can place the felling date for the trees used to make the tabernacle at c. AD 1489-1504.

Fig. 7. Berg tabernacle. Close-up view of a modern repair to the cabinet.

averages			Z1050049	Z105001a	Z105005a	Z105003a	Z1050029	Z105007a
Z105M002	plank 8	Z1050049	*	3.99	3.89	2.13	1.68	1.57
	plank 7	Z105001a	3.99	*	4.16	2.8	4.04	-
Z105M003	plank 9	Z105005a	3.89	4.16	*	5.66	3.06	2.24
	plank 5	Z105003a	2.13	2.8	5.66	*	2.04	\
	right door	Z1050029	1.68	4.04	3.06	2.04	*	4.29
	plank 1	Z105007a	1.57	-	2.24	\	4.29	*

Table 1. Berg tabernacle. Correlation between the tree-ring curves from each timber element with each other.

Oak provenance

Table 1 shows the correlation (t-value) between each tree-ring curve from the tabernacle with each other, at their cross-matched position. Significant correlation appears between the curves, and these are confirmed through visual comparison of the plotted tree-ring measurements. Due to the matching of the individual elements with a range of Northern European chronologies for oak, it is chosen to make two averages, one consisting of two timbers (Z105M002) of 183 years in length, the other of three (Z105M003) which is 213 years long. The correlation between the two averages is $t = 5.55$.

Table 2 shows the correlation between these two averages and a range of oak site and master chronologies for Northern Europe. Both chronologies are achieving high correlation with tree-ring data from the Southern Baltic region, but there seems to be a slight indication that the two are from slightly different sources within that region. The average Z105M003 is dating best with the so-called Baltic 1 chronology built from tree-ring data from painted panels (Hillam & Tyers 1995). This chronology is possibly from oaks from the region around the catchment area of the river Vistula. Average Z105M002 from the Berg tabernacle is matching more strongly with the Baltic 2 chronology. Baltic 2 is again made from tree-ring data from painted panels, but this material forms a separate group to Baltic 1. Geographically, we are still unsure as to a more specific provenance for this material, but it is also from the Southern Baltic region.

As the Berg tabernacle is made from Southern Baltic oaks a sapwood estimate for the region around the mouth of the Vistula River is used (c. 15 sapwood years (-6 +9) (Wazny 1990)).

Conclusion

The dendrochronological analysis of the Berg tabernacle is carried out wholly non-invasively, with success. The single analysed plank that could not be dated had an average ring width of 1.03mm, and a confident series of measurements could be attained. However the plank contained just 62 rings and this means that finding the dating for this tree-ring series is difficult.

All other elements analysed are dated. All the dated planks have an average ring width of between 1.05 and 1.37 mm. and contain between 82 and 208 rings, which helps in achieving successful dating results (fig. 8). We can combine this with the fact that good cross-matching was achieved between elements in the construction, so that accuracy control could be kept, allowing a very good success rate in contrast to that of the Skjervøy altarpiece, reported previously (*CATS dendro report 3* (Daly 2014a)).

In spite of the fact that no sapwood is preserved on the analysed timber elements of the tabernacle, some circumstantial evidence for possible sapwood is used to suggest an estimated felling date range for the trees used to make the piece, at c. AD 1489-1504.

Filenames	-	-	Z105M002	Z105M003	
-	start	dates	AD1297	AD1266	
-	dates	end	AD1479	AD1478	
Art-historical tree-ring data, Southern Baltic region					
0M040004	AD1156	AD1597	4.99	8.16	Baltic 1 (Hillam & Tyers 1995)
0M040005	AD1257	AD1615	9.79	6.36	Baltic 2 (Hillam & Tyers 1995)
0670113M	AD1344	AD1613	5.91	-	Baltic 3 (Tyers pers comm.)
0EQKTVM001	AD1295	AD1549	4.63	10.79	Tallinn Christ Money-lenders (Daly & Läänelaid 2012)
GAPCX7	AD1283	AD1450	4.16	10.20	Guthrie Aisle panels (Crone pers comm.)
Z103M003	AD1234	AD1495	6.48	7.42	Slagen altertavle Norge (Daly 2013b)
se629m01	AD1118	AD1386	-	6.99	York Minster (Tyers pers comm.)
stirlingdoorsM1	AD1270	AD1524	-	6.61	Stirling Castle Scotland doors (Crone pers comm.)
Z083M002	AD1359	AD1554	-	5.31	Susannah Unknown artist (Daly 2012)
os160_t7	AD1138	AD1382	4.53	5.01	York Vicars Choral Large Table (Tyers pers comm.)
HMC_T165	AD1078	AD1369	5.70	4.80	Hull boards from 37 coffins Yorkshire (Tyers pers comm.)
Z101M001	AD1317	AD1493	3.03	4.47	Kvæfjord 1 altertavle Norge back planks (Daly 2014b)
H11EOM01	AD1260	AD1495	4.39	4.37	Bordesholmer Altar (Hamburg uni., revised Daly 2007)
Z104004c	AD1230	AD1420	3.81	4.30	Skjervøy corpus back plank 2 (Daly 2014a)
se617M01	AD1100	AD1396	4.02	3.89	New Baxtergate Grims (Tyers pers comm.)
Site and master chronologies					
P815001M	AD1262	AD1503	4.83	8.75	Bielsk Podl. (Wazny pers comm.)
P734002M	AD1247	AD1427	3.78	8.24	Bransk (Wazny pers comm.)
P676001M	AD1067	AD1393	-	5.07	Kolobrzeg (Wazny pers comm.)
0628002M	AD1225	AD1445	7.47	4.77	Torun Joh Kir (Wazny pers comm.)
PM670108	AD725	AD1985	-	4.72	Gdansk (Wazny pers comm.)
P719M001	AD1309	AD1551	-	4.70	Tolknicko (Wazny pers comm.)
P720404M	AD1192	AD1452	5.48	4.15	Pultusk (Wazny pers comm.)
DM200005	AD915	AD1873	3.67	3.06	Niedersachsen; Nord (Göttingen Uni.)
Ship and barrel chronologies					
0075M0042012	AD1247	AD1455	-	8.25	Vejdyb ship Baltic 1 group 4 timber mean (Daly 1997)
0075M0012012	AD1113	AD1463	5.69	6.04	Vejdyb ship Baltic 1 group 16 timber mean (Daly 1997)
0075M0032012	AD1221	AD1456	8.78	4.28	Vejdyb ship Baltic 2 group 5 timber mean (Daly 1997)
Z076m003 all	AD1097	AD1393	5.22	5.93	Skjernøysund ship & cargo (Daly 2011)
Z129M001	AD1125	AD1399	3.52	5.67	Niels Hemmingsensgade barrel (Daly 2000)
Z005M002	AD1177	AD1356	-	5.46	Bølevraget ship Norge four beams (Daly & Nymoen 2008)
Z084M001	AD1152	AD1437	5.64	5.35	Skaftö ship barrels (Daly 2013a)
P0011009	AD1103	AD1403	4.03	5.14	Copper Ship- Wainscot (Wazny pers comm.)
Z054m001	AD1235	AD1448	4.05	4.83	Ostsee VII ship's planks (Daly 2010)
CLS2000	AD1110	AD1393	6.01	4.80	Hull Chapel Lane Yorkshire boat planks (Tyers pers comm.)
02071M01	AD1126	AD1414	7.22	4.73	Dokøen Copenhagen ship 2 (Eriksen 2001)

Table 2. Berg tabernacle, Oslo. Result of the correlation between the two average tree-ring curves from the tabernacle and diverse Northern European site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t-values.

Fig. 8. Berg tabernacle. Chart summarising the tree-ring data derived from the seven elements analysed, shown together with the Skjervøy altarpiece data (CATS *Dendro report* 3, Daly 2014a), for comparison.

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filename	sample title and number	rings	start yr.	end yr.	conversion	pith	sapwood	bark?	extra start	extra end	interpretation / felling
Z105001a	Berg tabernacle cabinet plank 7	178	AD1297	AD1474	T	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1484
Z1050029	Berg tabernacle right door plank	208	AD1271	AD1478	?	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1488
Z105003a	Berg tabernacle frame back plank 5	124	AD1266	AD1389	T	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1399
Z1050049	Berg tabernacle cabinet plank 8	134	AD1346	AD1479	T	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1489
Z105005a	Berg tabernacle cabinet plank 9	181	AD1287	AD1467	?	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1477
Z105006a	Berg tabernacle frame front plank 4	62			?	G	0	N	H1	H1	undated
Z105007a	Berg tabernacle frame front plank 1	82	AD1389	AD1470	?	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD1480
Z105M001	Berg tabernacle Norway 5 timber mean	214	AD1266	AD1479							
Z105M002	Berg tabernacle Norway 1&4 2 timber mean	183	AD1297	AD1479							
Z105M003	Berg tabernacle Norway 2 3&5 3 timber mean	213	AD1266	AD1478							
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings.											
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9th January 2013											

Table 3. Berg tabernacle, Oslo. List of objects analysed.